

A Cross-layer Monitoring Solution based on Quality Models

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Abstract: In order to implement cross-organizational workflows and to realize collaborations between small and medium enterprises (SMEs), the use of Web service technology, Service-Oriented Architecture and Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) has become a necessity. Based on these technologies, the need for monitoring the quality of (a) the acquired resources, (b) the services offered to the final users and (c) the workflow-based procedures used by SMEs in order to use services, has come to the fore. To tackle this need, we propose four metric Quality Models that cover quality terms for the Workflow, Service and Infrastructure layers and an additional one for expressing the equality and inter-dependency relations between the previous ones. To support these models we have implemented a cross-layer monitoring system, whose main advantages are the layer-specific metric aggregators and an event pattern discoverer for processing the monitoring log. Our evaluation is based on the performance and accuracy aspects of the proposed cross-layer monitoring system.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, many organizations form dynamic co-operations in order to effectively deal with market requirements. Companies focus on their core business and goals whilst outsourcing secondary activities to other organizations. To enable co-operation between organizations, the information processing infrastructures of the participating SMEs need to be linked. Workflow management systems that control the processes in the individual SMEs are a key feature. Moreover, in order to implement cross-organisational workflows and to realise collaborations between SMEs, the use of Web service technology and service-oriented architecture has become a necessity. Whilst, SMEs are continuously moving towards service-oriented infrastructures, the need of hosting them has raised an important issue for the quality of the underlying cloud infrastructures, the services offered to final users, as well as of the workflow-based procedures used by SMEs.

Cross-layer monitoring of Service-Based Applications (SBAs) is the continuous and closed loop procedure of measuring, monitoring, reporting, and improving the Quality of Service (QoS) of systems and applications delivered by service-oriented solutions. Monitoring involves several distinct activities including (a) logging and analysis of execution details of the workflow, service and infrastructure functional lay-

ers (b) obtaining metrics for each of one of them, (c) detecting situations that require management attention and (d) determining appropriate control actions. State-of-the-art research in this area reveals that most approaches are based on individual layers without considering the cross-layer dependencies (Zeginis et al., 2013) that Quality Models (QMs) might have (Seth et al., 2005). In order to address the quality aspects of a monitoring framework dealing with the three functional layers of a SBA (i.e. *Workflow, Service and Infrastructure*), we introduce a monitoring framework that is based on three layer-specific QMs, along with an additional dependency QM, catering for the cross-layer relationships between quality metrics defined in the three QMs. Finally, the proposed monitoring framework stands on top of our previous research work (Zeginis et al., 2015) that emphasizes on the processing of the aggregated monitoring data, so as to detect critical event patterns that lead to specific Service Level Objective (SLO) violations.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 summarizes the related work, Section 3 introduces the cross-layer monitoring framework, while Section 4 defines the QMs and Section 5 provide details for the quality metrics aggregation. Section 6 describes an event pattern detection mechanism, while Sections 7 and 8 provide implementation details and experimental results respectively. Finally, Section 9 concludes and provides future work directions.

2 RELATED WORK

Monitoring of SBAs have attracted the interest of many researchers in the recent years. Many approaches have been proposed, mainly at the Service layer, however most of them are fragmented and focus only on one layer disregarding the possible mapping of metric data values among the layers.

In (Alhamazani et al., 2015) researchers developed and validated CLAMBS, Cross-Layer Multi-Cloud Application Monitoring and Benchmarking as-a-Service for efficient QoS monitoring and benchmarking of cloud applications hosted on multi-clouds environments. Advantage of CLAMBS is its capability of monitoring and benchmarking individual application components, such as databases and web servers, distributed across cloud layers (*-aaS), spread among multiple cloud providers. In (Calero and Gutierrez, 2015), a novel monitoring architecture is addressed that deals with the aspect of cloud provider and cloud consumer. This architecture offers a monitoring PaaS to each cloud consumer that allows to customize the monitoring metrics. This is accomplished by the means of an adaptive distributed monitoring architecture automatically deployed in the cloud infrastructure. Kazhamiakin et al. (Kazhamiakin et al., 2009) define appropriate mechanisms and techniques to address monitoring in an integrated cross-layer framework. More precisely, they have stated the problem of cross-layer SBA monitoring and adaptation on a series of case studies and define the requirements for the integrated approaches that provide coherent solutions to monitor and adapt the whole application. In (Guinea et al., 2011), authors present an integrated approach for monitoring and adapting multi-layered SBAs. The approach comprises four main steps: a) monitoring and correlation, b) analysis of adaptation needs, c) identification of multi-layer adaptation strategies and d) adaptation enactment. Their main goal is to reveal correlations between what is being observed at the software and at the infrastructure layer to enable global system reasoning.

Many layer-specific approaches regarding QMs, (Joshi et al., 2011) (Cardoso et al., 2002) are based on stochastic models and probabilistic theory having as a major concern the scalability of the cloud resources based on quality metric results. Several approaches have been proposed capturing infrastructure QMs with focus on cloud resources. Authors in (Bardsiri and Hashemi, 2014) define QMs which support the evaluation of public cloud services; the validation of these QMs is performed according to empirical case studies without taking

into account the relations that Workflow Quality Model (WM), Infrastructure Quality Model (IM) and Service Quality Model (SM) can have between them. In (Gomez-Perez et al., 2013), the authors introduce the hypothesis that reliability of workflows can be notably improved by advocating scientists to preserve a minimal set of information that is essential to assist the interpretations of these workflows and hence improve their reproducibility and reusability. More precisely two quality dimensions were approached, (a) the stability of a workflow defined as a measurement of the ability of a workflow to preserve its properties through time and (b) the reliability of a workflow defined as a measurement for converging towards a scenario free of decay, i.e. complete and stable through time.

In order to state the advantages and disadvantages of the research approaches, we have conducted a comparison of the aforementioned approaches (Table 1), based on certain criteria indicating the support of quality metrics for each of the functional layers.

3 CROSS-LAYER MONITORING ARCHITECTURE

In (Zeginis et al., 2013) we have already proposed a cross-layer monitoring and adaptation framework for SBAs. In this section we introduce an enhanced framework (Figure 1) focusing on the monitoring part. The main idea of our approach is that measurements at different layers are encapsulated by sensors attached to respective layer-specific components and that these measurements are stored in databases. The core functionalities of this cross-layer monitoring framework are (i) gathering of monitoring data, (ii) assessment of monitoring data and (iii) storing them in a time-series database (TSDB) (Namiot, 2015).

The architecture of the proposed distributed monitoring framework consists of three Monitoring Managers for the Workflow, Service and Infrastructure layers. In each of these layers a metric aggregator and an assessment component exist, which are responsible for (a) collecting and calculating metric measurements based on the respective QM and (b) passing them to the assessment component which is responsible for the detection of specific Service Level Object (SLO) violations.

- Service and Infrastructure Monitoring managers provides the following functionalities
 - Aggregation of information based on the quality metrics that we defined in each of the layers.

Table 1: Comparison of monitoring research approaches.

	Business Layer	Workflow Layer	Infrastructure Layer	Service Layer	Cross-Layer Metric Dependencies
(Kazhamiakin et al., 2009)	✓		✓	✓	
(Guinea et al., 2011)			✓	✓	<i>partially</i>
(Gomez-Perez et al., 2013)		✓			
(Alhamazani et al., 2015)			✓	✓	
(Calero and Gutierrez, 2015)			✓	✓	
Proposed approach		✓	✓	✓	✓

Figure 1: Architecture of monitoring framework.

- Assessment of the aggregated information in order to detect SLO violations.
- Storing of the aggregated data to the management database. According to the level of the aggregation being supported where in this case we selected to store metric data in TSBD instances.
- As the cross-layer dependencies have been spotted, Service and Infrastructure managers propagates the measurement in the instance of WM in order to fill possible metric values that where identified during the cross-layer dependency done. The propagation is done from lower to higher levels e.g, SM to WM.
- The Workflow Monitoring manager additionally supports:
 - The functionality of a dependency aggregator which actually implements the cross-layer dependency model that has been defined. We have

added this required functionality on the Workflow Monitor Manager in order to expose cross-layer dependencies detected within the same public cloud sector.

Finally, the Cross-Layer Dependency Metrics Aggregator collects metrics from the three layers and aggregated information indicating the cross-layer dependencies and provides the following functionalities: (a) publish the SLO violations to the adaptation engine in order to decide on the best adaptation actions, (b) infers the detected patterns of monitoring data to the Pattern Discoverer implemented in (Zeginis et al., 2013).

4 QUALITY MODELS

As already introduced in (Metallidis et al., 2016), quality metric models, quality metrics, calculation formulas and particular types of metric relationships are defined in a formal way in order to indicate the structure of the respective layer. We have structurally separated the quality terms in two major categories: (i) **Quality dimensions** describe the quality aspect which can be used to provide an aspect-specific partition of quality terms. Quality dimensions are independent of the layer that a term maps to, (ii) **Quality attributes** are properties of an object which are measured by metrics.

At the Workflow layer we define four main quality dimensions: (i) time, (ii) cost, (iii) reliability, and (iv) security. Time quality dimension is a fundamental aspect of performance that describes the time needed in order to measure, execute, record, respond and traverse through operations. Cost quality dimension represents the cost associated with operations (e.g the provision of VM) and the execution of procedures. It is an important factor to evaluate whether organization still follows precisely their financial plan. Reliability dimension refers to the likelihood that a component (e.g workflow, task, service) will not malfunction

or fail during the workflow execution. Finally, security quality dimension indicates the degree at which components and systems are free from unauthorized accesses or change, subject to policy.

At the Service layer we define five main quality dimensions: (i) performance, (ii) stability, (iii) scalability, (iv) elasticity and (v) security. The performance dimension refers to the velocity of a Web service to respond to any request. Stability quality dimension indicates the ability to provide reliable, continuous, adaptable, consistent and recoverable services despite undesired situations like increased load, congestion, system failure and natural disasters. Service scalability (Herbst et al., 2013) is defined as the ability of a service to scale when additional workload is received to still keep up with the SLOs promised (e.g., when reaching maximum capacity for the service, the capability of the application encompassing additional resources in order to still satisfy its performance goals). Similarly, elasticity quality dimension is the degree at which a software system is able to autonomously scale the amount software instances or stretch the current VMs exploited (scale up) based on workload fluctuations e.g when the client expects to call a service (possibly multiple times) and gets a result according to the respective quality constraints posed. Finally, security dimension describes the means of providing AAA (auditability, authorisability and authenticity), confidentiality, and non-reputability (Trimintzios,).

At the Infrastructure layer we define five quality attributes: (i) performance, (ii) networking, (iii) CPU utilization, (iv) memory and storage, (v) PaaS/IaaS scalability and elasticity and one quality dimension for security. Performance quality attribute is being used in order to characterize the underlying clouds infrastructure performance in terms of response times upon actions of VM deployment/redeployment, software deployment/re-deployment, migration of service instances between different VMs and replication of software components between types of different VMs. Networking quality attribute characterizes the quality of network between a data center's SaaS/Application provider and the client of SaaS. Bandwidth quality attribute characterizes the volume of information per unit of time that a transmission medium (e.g., I/O device, Network Interface Controller) can handle. Quality attribute of CPU utilization depicts the level at which processors are being leveraged within a cloud infrastructure in favor of a client under the two different types of hypervisors. For accessing and storing data we have defined metrics for the quality attributes of memory and storage for the following types: RAM and Hard Disks. PaaS/IaaS Scalability is the ability of the underly-

ing infrastructure to sustain increasing workloads by making use of additional resources, which are directly requested, including all the hardware and virtualization layers. The differentiation from the security quality dimensions at the service layer is that we consider system components like VMs instead of service components in order to calculate the corresponding metrics.

To formalize relationships between quality metrics across the three layer-specific QMs we have considered an initial set of cross-layer dependencies in the form of a Dependency Quality Model. These dependencies indicate that (a) the computation of a metric at one layer can be used for the (partial) computation of a relevant metric at another layer and (b) metric values from different layers that are inter-dependent, for example the high or low value of a metric in one layer can affect the value of a metric in another layer. Relevance could map to either both metrics belonging to the same quality dimension, or being described by similar quality attributes. The measurability of all metrics defined is guaranteed via the cross-layer dependencies of the metric aggregation formulas and the fact that raw quality metrics with no dependencies can be calculated by sensors placed by the distributed monitoring system on one of the respective layers.

5 QUALITY METRICS AGGREGATION

The proposed monitoring framework comprises three metric aggregators, responsible for gathering the layer-specific metric values and pushing them to the time-series database. The service layer aggregator depicted in Figure 2 performs aggregation in four steps. In the first step, Prometheus API client¹, is used for monitoring the service layer client calls by retrieving raw metric data. Then, at the aggregation phase the aggregator calculates the raw metric data and aggregates them based on the definitions of composite metrics made in SM, whilst on the third step metric values are being pulled from KairosDB² time-series database in case they are required for the calculation of data metrics based on historic data values, (Metallidis et al., 2016). At the final step the aggregator pushes the values of raw and composite metrics to the TSDB.

The Infrastructure layer aggregator similarly performs aggregation in three steps (Figure 3). In the first step, we use JSON Exporter of Nagios monitor-

¹<https://prometheus.io/>

²<https://kairosdb.github.io/>

Figure 2: Architecture of Service layer aggregator.

Figure 3: Architecture of Infrastructure layer aggregator.

ing tool³ and appropriate Java client libraries that manipulate JSON objects, in order to retrieve data for each of the raw metrics. At the second step the aggregation of the composite metrics takes place. We aggregate and push metrics every one minute, in order to be uniform with the frequency selection of service layer aggregator which also aggregates and push values every minute. Aggregations are performed outside KairosDB, in plain Java classes, as the possible usage of a KairosDB aggregator would add unnecessary complexity to the implementation of the aggregator. At the third step we push the composite metric data to the KairosDB.

There is a separation of the workflow aggregator and the dependency aggregator although in our implementation they are deployed on the same VM. The workflow aggregator collects raw metrics at the workflow layer and then aggregate them as soon as the workflow reaches the endpoint. In order to provide runtime monitoring, we have used the *Listeners* that Activiti⁴ workflow engine offers. When the flow reaches the endpoint, then a listener is responsible for the collection and aggregation of the metrics. Listeners are the major components in the procedure of monitoring at the Workflow layer. The reason that both of the workflows have the same endpoint in Figure 4, is that the collection and aggregation part is the same for all the workflows operating within the workflow management engine. On the second step, as soon as the the aggregations are completed, we use

³<https://www.nagios.org/>

⁴<http://activiti.org/>

the KairosDB client API which makes the appropriate calls on the KairosDB instance of the workflow layer VM. We have decided to perform the gathering of the metric information on the endpoint of each of the workflows, that is a sign that they have completed successfully. However, in cases of failures, Activiti provides an in-memory database where historic values are stored during the execution of each of the tasks, thus we can retrieve possible lost values from the aforementioned database.

There are two types of cross-layer dependencies that we take into consideration in our approach, (i) dependencies between the Service layer and the Workflow layer metrics and (ii) dependencies between the Infrastructure layer and the Service layer metrics. Thus, the cross-layer dependency aggregator is responsible for collecting the dependency metrics and for calculating the respective metric value at the higher layer. In order to pass the dependency metrics from lower to higher layers, we have used a publish/subscribe system. For instance, if we are interested in a dependency metric between the service and the workflow layers, as the service monitoring system generates a number of raw and composite metric values, we should limit the retrieved metrics to the ones that concerns the executed workflow instance. To achieve this, the publisher passes only the values of the dependency occurred during the execution of the specific workflow instance. Once the dependency values of the composite cross-layer dependency metrics are calculated, they are pushed to the local database.

6 PROCESSING THE MONITORING LOG

Once aggregators have retrieved and stored the aggregated metric values to the central time-series database, the event pattern detection components starts traversing the execution log in order to detect critical event patterns that might lead to violations of composite SLOs. In a previous work (Zeginis et al., 2015) we have introduced a logical approach to discover such type of event patterns. Very briefly, in this approach we proposed an offline deterministic algorithm for discovering frequent event patterns (i.e. as-

Figure 4: Architecture of Workflow aggregator.

sociation rules) leading to critical events of a specific metric. This algorithm is based on propositional logic and takes into consideration both the dependencies of the components constituting the multi-Cloud application system and the aggregate metrics extracted by the TSDB. In particular, the algorithm requires as input: (i) the monitoring log, (ii) the metric we are interested in identifying critical event patterns and, (iii) the metrics classification (i.e. success, warning, critical), that is part of the aggregated event. As it is obvious, all these required input is provided by the proposed monitoring framework, and especially can be extracted by the incorporating TSDB, the monitoring sensors and the aggregators. The algorithm exploits contingency tables, i.e. tables displaying the frequency distributions of the candidate patterns and their negations as antecedents and the specified metric event, as well as its negation as consequences. The entries of these tables are utilized to determine the association rules.

The event pattern discovery enables both proactive and reactive adaptation. Proactive adaptation is achieved by detecting the critical event patterns causing service failures as early as possible in order to prevent future critical SLO violations. The detected patterns are mapped to suitable adaptation strategies in the form of adaptation rules, that are fired immediately in order to prevent a possible SLO violation. Furthermore, the proposed framework can also react immediately on detected critical events, thus performing also reactive adaptation on the running SBA. Upon the detection of a SLO violation, the Adaptation Rule Manager immediately fires the corresponding adaptation rule, dictating the application of a specific adaptation action. Some predefined simple rules, mapping critical events to specific adaptation actions, are manually produced by the SBA Adaptation Manager (usually the SBA provider herself/himself) and are passed to the Adaptation Rule Manager.

7 IMPLEMENTATION

In order to realize the proposed monitoring framework we came up with some decisions on the monitoring tools to be used for each of the three layers. Regarding the Infrastructure layer, we used Nagios monitoring tool, which is the Industry Standard in IT infrastructure monitoring, offering various monitoring sensors. As far as monitoring is concerned on the service layer, we have conducted a review on existing monitoring solutions (Prometheus, Influxdata⁵, statsD (Graphite)⁶, scollector (Bosun)⁷ and freeware versions of Datadog⁸ and New Relic⁹), based on a set of criteria: (i) commercial / open source, (ii) the local domain support, which represents the possibility of the monitoring tools offering monitoring capabilities in a localhost domain, (iii) the limit of recorded monitoring events, (iv) the definition of custom metrics in order to measure specific software components, (v) the support of Real User Monitoring (RUM)¹⁰ which is a major factor of computing response times and finally (vi) if it a standalone solution, as we cater for monitoring tools that do not depend on third party back-end components. From this comparison (Table 2) we decided to use Prometheus, which satisfies all the required criteria.

At the workflow layer, we have decided to use Activiti, which is an open source Business and Workflow engine framework that provides an environment for running workflows and business processes. It provides us with useful functionalities, such as the provision of a web-based modeling tool for workflow and

⁵<https://www.influxdata.com/>

⁶<https://github.com/etsy/statsd>

⁷<http://bosun.org/scollector/>

⁸<https://www.datadoghq.com/>

⁹<https://newrelic.com/>

¹⁰https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Real_user_monitoring

Table 2: Service Monitoring tools comparison.

	Open source	Local domain Support	Unlimited Storage	Custom Metrics	Support of Real User Monitoring	Standalone
Datadog		✓		✓		✓
New Relic		✓				✓
Prometheus	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Influxdata	✓	✓	✓			
statsD (Graphite)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
scollector (Bosun)	✓	✓	✓	✓		

business analysts, an Eclipse plug-in for developers¹¹ and a web application for managing workflow components. Other similar workflow engines are jBPM¹² and BonitaSoft¹³. The main difference between Activiti and these workflow engines is that the Activiti project provides well-structured environment in order to work with, making this way a lot easier for the developers to design and sustain their workflows.

8 EVALUATION

In this section we provide experimental results of the proposed monitoring solution. The main purpose of these experiments are to measure its performance and accuracy. The setup of the virtual machines used in these experiments is the following: Workflow instances of the running examples were carried out in two cloud infrastructures. The first one is a private cloud infrastructure offered by the PaaS of VMWare in which we have provisioned four VMs hosted by a PC with Intel Core i7-4 Cores 2.50 GHz, 16 GB Ram, 300 GB SSD Hard Disk, running Windows 10 64-bit Operating System (OS). Two VMs were provisioned with characteristics of 2 vCPUs, 2 GB Ram, 15 GB hard disk and OS of Centos7 64-bit. The remaining two VMs had the characteristics of 2 vCPUs, 4 GB RAM and 20 GB hard disk and OS of Centos7 64-bit. In a public cloud infrastructure we have used one VM with of 2 vCPUs, 4 GB RAM, 100 GB Hard Disk drive and OS of Ubuntu 14.04 64 bit to host the central TSDB.

In the first experiment we measure the *average response times* of the set of services of fortress-web application¹⁴ with different amounts of workloads for each of the users accessing the services simultaneously. Firstly, we ran the workflow with a 20 requests/min workload for each set of simultaneous

¹¹<http://docs.alfresco.com/4.1/tasks/wf-install-activiti-designer.html>

¹²<https://www.jbpm.org/>

¹³<http://www.bonitasoft.com/>

¹⁴<http://directory.apache.org/fortress/>

Figure 5: Average response time for simultaneous users.

Figure 6: Accuracy of the monitoring system.

users and then we follow the same pattern for 40 requests/min and 60 requests/min workloads.

As expected, the response time is increasing according to the number of simultaneous users and the number of workload requests/min. Figure 5 indicates that there is an increasing difference between the number of simultaneous users. In the workload of 40 requests/min the difference between two and four simultaneous users is bigger than 60ms and for the workload of 60 requests/min is even bigger than 70ms. This indicates that the of response time between the different numbers of simultaneous users is bigger than the amount of workload that the services can tolerate. The reason behind this could be the number of simultaneous threads that Java instantiates in order to serve the requests, thus having a late response time.

In our second experiment we evaluated the accuracy of the distributed monitoring system. This experiment is based on seven executions, each one which corresponds to a workflow instance. For each

execution we calculated the accuracy of the monitoring system, produce by dividing the number of $\frac{Metrics+Datapoints(received)}{Metrics+Datapoints(expected)}$. These executions were conducted with a workload of 60 requests/min and for each one of them we increased the number of users (one per time). As we can observe in Figure 6 the system does not fail under 90% of accuracy. The 10% percent loss of metrics and datapoints is due to the pulling frequency of the monitoring system.

9 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we have introduced a monitoring framework, that covers three main layers of a SBA, i.e. infrastructure, service and workflow layers. To achieve this we propose the corresponding layer-specific quality models that define a set of metrics that can be monitored in each layer. Moreover, in the proposed framework we introduce the metric aggregators for each layer as the components that computes composite metrics values from the raw ones produced by the monitoring sensors and stores them in a times-series database, to be further processed by the event-pattern detection component.

As for future work, we plan to introduce a complex cross-layer adaptation engine that will efficiently manage the SLO violations both reactively and proactively by exploiting the detected critical event patterns. Furthermore, a future objective is the creation of a Business quality model, with regard to the Business functional layer which could include quality terms related to the quality of the business processes and higher level Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

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¹⁵<http://www.cloudsocket.eu>